

PUBLIC SPEAKING SKILLS IN EDUCATION IN THE 21st CENTURY: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstrak: Kemampuan untuk mengartikulasikan ide dengan jelas dan melibatkan audiens tidak hanya penting untuk kesuksesan akademis, tetapi juga untuk upaya profesional di masa depan. Oleh karena itu, pengembangan keterampilan public speaking merupakan bagian integral dari lanskap pendidikan. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengevaluasi pentingnya keterampilan berbicara di depan umum dalam konteks pendidikan abad ke-21 dengan melakukan tinjauan sistematis terhadap literatur yang relevan. Dengan menggunakan pendekatan *Systematic Literature Review* (SLR), penelitian ini menganalisis berbagai penelitian yang membahas *public speaking* dari sudut pandang pendidik dan peserta didik. Basis data yang digunakan untuk tinjauan ini adalah Google Scholar, yang menyediakan akses ke berbagai artikel ilmiah. Sebanyak 9 artikel yang diterbitkan antara tahun 2020 dan 2024 dimasukkan dalam analisis ini, berdasarkan kriteria inklusi tertentu. Strategi pencarian menggunakan kata kunci seperti “kemampuan *public speaking* pendidik” dan “kemampuan *public speaking* peserta didik.” Teknik analisis data tematik digunakan untuk mengidentifikasi tema-tema utama dalam literatur yang dipilih. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa kemampuan *public speaking* memainkan peran penting dalam meningkatkan kualitas pembelajaran. Pendidik dengan *public speaking* yang kuat dapat menumbuhkan lingkungan belajar yang lebih interaktif, memotivasi siswa, dan menyampaikan materi secara efektif. Bagi peserta didik, *public speaking* berkontribusi pada pengembangan kepercayaan diri, pemikiran kritis, dan keterampilan komunikasi. Namun, ada kesenjangan yang nyata dalam penelitian mengenai pengembangan kemampuan *public speaking* bagi pendidik. Penelitian ini menggarisbawahi perlunya program pelatihan yang berkelanjutan dan terintegrasi untuk memenuhi kebutuhan para pendidik dalam meningkatkan kompetensi komunikasi mereka. Temuan baru dalam penelitian ini menghasilkan 3 poin penting dipelুকannya *public speaking* bagi pendidik, yaitu sebagai Motivator, Katalisator, Fasilitator.

Kata Kunci: *Public Speaking Skill, Education, 21st Century*

Abstract: The ability to clearly articulate ideas and engage an audience is not only essential for academic success, but also for future professional endeavors. Therefore, the development of public speaking skills is an integral part of the educational landscape. This study aims to evaluate the importance of public speaking skills in the context of 21st century education by conducting a systematic review of relevant literature. Using a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach, this research analyzes various studies that address public speaking from the perspective of educators and learners. The database used for this review was Google Scholar, which provides access to a wide range of scholarly articles. A total of 9 articles published between 2020 and 2024 were included in this analysis, based on specific inclusion criteria. The search strategy used keywords such as “educators’ public speaking skills” and “learners’ public speaking skills.” Thematic data analysis techniques were used to identify key themes in the selected literature. The results showed that public speaking skills play an important role in improving the quality of learning. Educators with strong public speaking skills can foster a more interactive learning environment, motivate students and deliver materials effectively. For learners, public speaking contributes to the development of self-confidence, critical thinking and communication skills. However, there is a noticeable gap in research regarding the development of public speaking skills among educators. This research underscores the need for sustainable and integrated training programs to meet the needs of educators in improving their communication competencies. The new findings in this study resulted in 3 important points, namely the need to be an important point in public speaking for educators, namely as a Motivator, Catalyst, Facilitator.
Keywords: *Public Speaking Skill, Education, 21st Century*

A. INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, public speaking ability is one of the important competencies that must be possessed by every individual, especially in the world of education (Kain et al., 2024). This century is known for new challenges and dynamics that require mastery of 21st century skills, namely 4C: Critical Thinking, Communication, Collaboration, and Creativity (Arnyana, 2019). One of the mastery that must be owned by educators and learners in the world of education in the 21st century is Communication or Public Speaking. Public Speaking is an important skill that every educator and learner must have because it serves as a foundation for success for educators in facilitating the learning process and also the success of students in the learning process (Hamzah & Oktavia, 2022).

Public speaking is an individual's ability to articulate or convey a topic of discussion in front of many people (Resti Wiratami et al., 2022). Public speaking is defined as the ability to convey information effectively to an audience (Herbein et al., 2018). In the era of globalization marked by technological advances and information disclosure, public speaking skills are increasingly essential for both students and educators (Hamzah & Oktavia, 2022).

The current phenomenon shows that more attention is being paid to developing learners' public speaking skills. Various studies and trainings are held to improve learners' skills in public speaking, especially in the context of debate competitions, presentations, and other extracurricular activities (Syafuruddin et al., 2023). However, on the educator side, research on the importance of public speaking skills in learning activities is still relatively minimal. In fact, educators have a strategic role in delivering material and facilitating the teaching and learning process effectively through good speaking skills.

Some previous studies have highlighted the importance of public speaking in education, but the main focus of the study still revolves around skill development among students. For example, research conducted by (Rahmaniah & AR, 2022) used a quasi-experimental method with a pre-test and post-test design to measure the impact of public speaking training on learners' communication skills. Before the training, learners'

communication skills were in the medium category, with relatively low levels of fluency in responding to opinions and confidence. However, statistical analysis conducted by t-test showed a significant improvement after the training, where learners' communication skills increased to the high category, especially in topic understanding and fluency in responding to opinions. The confidence in public speaking also improved although it was still in the medium category. This study justifies its results by referring to active learning theory which states that direct involvement in communication practices can accelerate the mastery of speaking skills.

Similarly, a study (Azmi et al., 2024), used a mixed-methods approach by combining quantitative and qualitative analysis to evaluate the impact of public speaking training on children's language skills. The post-test results showed significant improvements in learners' self-confidence and communication skills. In justifying the results, the study utilized in-depth interviews that revealed participants' experiences during the training, which indicated that public speaking not only improved verbal skills, but also formed a deeper understanding of effective communication structures. The epistemological support from these two studies shows that public speaking training not only helps develop practical skills, but also provides a cognitive framework that supports overall communication skills in both academic and social settings.

From these two perspectives, it can be concluded that public speaking skills have an important contribution in honing learners' communication skills, increasing their self-confidence, and broadening their horizons regarding social interaction, with strong justification through epistemological approaches that support their research results.

The research revealed by (Hamzah & Oktavia, 2022) based on the research revealed that the utilization of public speaking by educators is able to encourage students to engage in active learning and maintain focus on the subject matter as evidenced by the empirical data collected. Qualitative research with a case study approach at SMPIT Al Fikri Islamic Green School Pekanbaru shows that educators who use public speaking effectively can make students more excited and enthusiastic in participating in lessons, especially in Islamic Religious Education (PAI) subjects. This is reinforced by research revealed by (Syafuruddin et al., 2023) that speaking skills training for educators resulted in a significant

improvement in their ability to speak in public. After attending the training, the educators became better able to attract the attention of the audience through an interesting presentation style and convey messages more effectively. They also showed improvement in maintaining positive interactions with listeners. In addition, the training proved to increase the educators' confidence when performing in public. Thus, formal training in public speaking proved to be an effective method to improve educators' speaking skills.

From the above opinions, it can be concluded that public speaking skills are very important for educators, because with these skills, educators can encourage learners' engagement in active learning, maintain their focus on the material, and help learners assimilate information better. In addition, public speaking training has also been proven to improve educators' ability to deliver messages effectively, attract audience attention, maintain positive interactions, and increase confidence when speaking in public (Nelani Khairun & Dodi Pasila Putra, 2023).

The main problem faced today is the lack of attention to the development of public speaking skills in educators. Many studies have focused on strengthening this competency among learners, but not many have explored how important it is for educators to have the same skills. Along with the changing educational paradigm that demands educators to be more creative, innovative and communicative, public speaking skills are key in creating a more interactive and meaningful learning experience. If educators are not equipped with adequate public speaking skills, the effectiveness of the learning process can be hampered (Sholichah et al., 2022). Thus, this gap encourages the importance of a more in-depth study of public speaking skills for educators.

Three questions were asked: 1) Has existing research adequately addressed the importance of public speaking skills in 21st century education? 2) How does public speaking training affect the improvement of educators' and learners' speaking skills? 3) What are the gaps in research related to developing educators' public speaking skills, and what recommendations can be made to address them?

B. RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method. The purpose of this research is to evaluate public speaking skills in 21st century education, by reviewing journals relevant to the topic. SLR was chosen as the research design because it provides a comprehensive view of previous research results. The participants in this study are not individuals, but scientific articles available on the Google Scholar platform. The articles were selected based on their relevance to the theme of public speaking skills in 21st century education. These articles served as the main source of data analyzed. The instrument in this study is the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) procedure used to ensure a transparent and systematic literature review process. The data collection process began with searching for articles using relevant keywords, then the articles found were selected and categorized based on their relevance to the research theme. Data analysis was conducted by following the five steps of PRISMA, namely searching, filtering, initial data, feasibility, and final data (Muhaimin et al., 2023). The data collected from the articles was organized into matrix tables to aid in further analysis. This process enabled the identification of trends, gaps and key findings from the various articles reviewed. The data analysis technique used in this study was thematic analysis, where the data from the identified articles were organized and classified based on key themes related to public speaking skills in 21st century education. Here are the keywords and article criteria:

Table 1.1 Keyword and Article Criteria

No	Keyword and Article Criteria
1	Educators' public speaking skills and students' public speaking skills
2	Artikel publish 2020-2024
3	Journal only, does not include thesis
4	In Indonesian and English

The following are the results of the identification of articles related to the theme “public speaking skills in 21st century education”

Table 1.2

C. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis showed that 9 articles met the data analysis criteria, 6 articles examining the public speaking skills of students, and 3 articles examining the public speaking skills of educators. This study is limited to public speaking skills in the scope of education.

Table 2. Articles or Reviewed Literature

No	Author	Purpose	Research Method	Population/Place of Learning	Findings
1	Nurhafida Rahmaniah, Rezki Amaliyah AR	Describe public speaking skills based on the value of social interaction and self-confidence.	Field study	STUDENTS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL 1 TINAMBUNG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public speaking training at SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung succeeded in improving students' communication skills. There were significant improvements in communication skills, topic comprehension, fluency in responding, and confidence after the training
2	Muhammad Mursyid, Yono	Exploring the impact of the muhadharah program on public speaking skills	Qualitative Descriptive	MAJLIS TA'LIM RIYADUL HASANKA KP. KEBON KOPI.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The existence of muhadharah activities can train students' courage, self-confidence and speech skills in speaking in front of the crowd.
3	Suci Hayati, Dina Anika Marhayani, Abd. Basith	Describe the level of self-confidence and public speaking ability of grade V students at SD Negeri 94 Singkawang and analyze the relationship between the two.	Quantitative Approach	Grade V students of SDN 94 Singkawang	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is a significant relationship between self-confidence and public speaking skills with a correlation value of 0.786 in the high or strong category. This means that every increase in students' self-confidence will be followed by an increase in students' public speaking skills.
4	Nurwahyu Nengtias, Muya Barida, Niken Susilowati	Describing Public Speaking Skills through Sociodrama Technique	-Quantitative descriptive -Observation -Questionnaire	Grade XI students at SMA Negeri 4 Yogyakarta	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There was an increase in students' public speaking skills. Marked by the results of the pre-test 41% of students who have Public Speaking skills then in cycle I increased by 63.8% of students and cycle II by 86.1% of students.
5	Silva Nurlaila Qodar Wati, Ratnasari Dyah Utami	Describe how the application of the quantum teachin model to train	- Qualitative descriptive - Observation	SD Muhammadiyah 16 Surakarta	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research conducted at SD Muhammadiyah 16 Surakarta shows that educators train the public speaking skills

No	Author	Purpose	Research Method	Population/Place of Learning	Findings
6	Lefrant Oriville Bartolomeus Albertus, Reynita Ardiana Nurasid, Bagus Cahyo Shah Adhi Pradana	students' public speaking skills and how the obstacles and solutions faced by educators. Measuring the effect of a public speaking teaching program on students' self-confidence	Quantitative descriptive	-Hanura Bina Putra Elementary School students in grade 5 -Students of Kawung 1 Middle School, Surabaya, class 9	of upper class students using the quantum teaching model and discussion methods once a week on certain subjects. • There is an influence of a public speaking program on students' self-confidence.
7	Winda Hardyanti, Frida Kusumastuti, Joko Susilo	Describe strengthening communication skills through public speaking training for elementary school educators	- Observation - Field study	Elementary School Educator at SDN Girimoyo 2, Karangploso District, Malang Regency	• Developing communication skills for elementary school educators can be done through intensive training which includes basic communication skills assistance, training as a presenter (MC) both formal and non-formal, as well as direct practice in public speaking.
8	Hamzah, Yanissya Oktavia	To find out the public speaking abilities of educators in learning Islamic Religious Education at SMPIT Al Fikri Islamic Green School Pekanbaru	- Qualitative - Case study - Observation - Interview - Documentation	PAI Educator at SMPIT Al Fikri Islamic Green School Pekanbaru	• Public speaking has a big influence on the enthusiasm and enthusiasm of students in understanding the material presented by educators.
9	Ayu Rahmawati Sam, Agus, Abd. Rajab	Public Speaking Skills of Class V Educators in Carrying Out Learning	- Qualitative - Observation - Interview - Documentation	Class V educator at SDN 261 Bilamporoa	• Public speaking skills have been implemented by class V educators at SDN 261 Bilamporoa, which allows students to understand the lesson well.

1. The Urgency of Public Speaking Skills in 21st Century Education

In the 21st-century education era, public speaking skills have become one of the important competencies for the education world. As expressed in the research by (Sam et al., 2024), public speaking skills enable teachers to create an interactive and engaging learning environment. In the context of education that increasingly emphasizes active student participation, this ability plays a crucial role in managing the classroom and delivering material clearly. Teachers who possess good public speaking skills can utilize flexible speaking techniques and appropriate intonation to capture students' attention, thereby enhancing their understanding of the material being taught.

Meanwhile, research conducted by (Hamzah & Oktavia, 2022) emphasizes that, public speaking skills not only function to convey information, but also to motivate students to learn actively. In education that demands student involvement, teachers need to master effective communication techniques, including mastery of material and dynamic interaction. Thus, public speaking skills become an essential tool in facilitating a more effective and engaging teaching and learning process for students.

However, while these two studies provide great insight into the application of public speaking in face-to-face learning, there are challenges that need to be faced, especially in the context of increasingly virtual learning. In this situation, teachers need to be able to adapt to different technologies and teaching methods, while still maintaining the quality of communication and interaction with students. Therefore, mastering public speaking skills in the 21st century is not only relevant in the physical classroom, but also in distance teaching, where engaging and effective interaction remains key to the success of the learning process.

In contrast to the study that examines the urgency of public speaking skills for educators, the urgency of learners' public speaking skills in the study conducted by (Rahmaniah & AR, 2022) lies in its role in developing self-confidence and active engagement in the learning process. This study shows that public speaking not only improves learners' communication skills, but also motivates them to actively participate in discussions and presentations, which are key elements in effective learning.

In addition, research conducted by (Mursyid & Yono, 2022) highlighted that public speaking skills give learners the opportunity to hone their critical thinking and analytical skills. By practicing public speaking, they learn to construct logical arguments and convey their ideas clearly. y practicing public speaking, they learn to construct logical arguments and convey their ideas clearly. This is very relevant in an educational context that emphasizes the development of 21st century competencies, such as Critical Thinking, Communication, Collaboration, and Creativity.

The literature review above shows that public speaking is a very important skill in 21st century education, both for educators and students. Educators who are proficient in public speaking can create an interactive and engaging learning environment, motivate students to be actively involved, foster critical thinking, and improve the quality of communication in the classroom (Kuntoro, 2023). Public speaking skills in 21st century education are not only useful for teachers in delivering material in an interesting way, but also play a role in building good relationships with students. Teachers who are able to speak confidently and openly in front of the class tend to more easily establish two-way communication with students. This creates an inclusive and supportive learning environment, where students feel more comfortable to ask questions, express opinions, and convey their ideas (Pentury et al., 2024).

On the other hand, public speaking skills for learners serve as a tool to develop self-confidence, critical thinking skills, and engagement in the learning process. Public speaking skills in the 21st century also support the development of soft skills that are needed in various fields (Ummah BK et al., 2024). In project-based learning, for example, students often need to present their work to both teachers and classmates. This activity provides an opportunity for students to practice their public speaking skills, manage their nervousness and build their confidence. Students who are skilled in public speaking tend to be more active in discussions and presentations, which is highly relevant to 21st century competency needs such as collaboration and communication (Kulish, 2022).

Public speaking skills for students also play an important role in preparing them for the demands of the workforce. In the era of globalization and intense competition, the ability to communicate effectively in public has become one of the valuable assets sought

by many employers (Wolverton & Tanner, 2019). Thus, public speaking is not only an academic skill, but also fundamental for career success in various fields. Therefore, there is a need to integrate public speaking skills in the education curriculum to prepare students to face future challenges with confidence and adequate skills.

2. Impact of Public Speaking Training on Speaking Skill Development

In relation to the development of public speaking skills, training programs have been proven to help students and teachers better understand effective communication techniques, so that they are able to convey ideas and information better. Along with the results of research by (Albertus et al., 2024) found that public speaking training programs in schools have a positive influence on student confidence. Students who participated in this training showed improved ability to communicate in public, as well as more confidence in interacting with others. Public speaking is considered an essential skill in the modern era because it can open up opportunities and improve students' networking ability, which in turn has an impact on their learning performance.

Meanwhile, research by (Wati & Utami, 2022) showed that the Quantum Teaching learning model with discussion methods was able to train students' public speaking skills at SD Muhammadiyah 16 Surakarta. In the study, public speaking training was applied regularly through the discussion method, where students were encouraged to express their opinions in an interactive and fun atmosphere. This proved to not only increase students' courage to speak in front of the class, but also improve their ability to convey ideas with confidence.

This is supported by research that has been conducted (Hayati et al., 2024) which shows a significant relationship between self-confidence and public speaking skills in grade V students at SD Negeri 94 Singkawang. With a correlation of 0.786, students who have higher self-confidence tend to have better public speaking skills. Overall, this study shows that public speaking training plays an important role in improving public speaking skills, as well as increasing self-confidence which is an important element in the learning process.

Meanwhile, the impact of public speaking training on educators in a study conducted by (Hardyanti et al., 2024) showed that public speaking training has a significant impact on the development of speaking skills, especially in the context of education as applied to teachers at SDN 2 Girimoyo. The training aimed to improve teachers' verbal communication skills, both face-to-face and virtually. After attending the training, which covered public speaking etiquette, formal and non-formal MC practice, and virtual public speaking, the teachers showed significant improvement in their ability to deliver material in a more structured and clear manner. This is evident from the increase in the average post-test score which shows a better understanding of public speaking concepts. In addition, the training also helped the teachers to be more confident and effective in interacting with students and parents, thus creating a more cooperative and engaging learning atmosphere.

Through the research literature reviewed above, it can be concluded that public speaking training plays a crucial role in the development of speaking skills, which is a vital element in the educational process and social interaction in the modern era. However, there are challenges and obstacles in the implementation of public speaking training, such as the speaker must be able to make their audience enthusiastic and interested in the topic discussed, many people still experience fear or nervousness (Marani, 2021), lack of confidence, and lack of practice and knowledge. Despite these challenges, the importance of public speaking as a tool to improve the quality of education and social interaction cannot be underestimated.

3. Gaps in Research and Development of Public Speaking Skills for Educators

Diagram 1. Differences in the percentage of public speaking at each level of education

Based on the diagram presented, there is a difference in the proportion of roles between teachers and learners in public speaking activities at each level of education. However, although the roles of teachers and learners vary, there is still a significant gap in the development of public speaking skills for educators. This is important to discuss, given that good communication skills are a key element in creating effective and interactive learning experiences. This gap can impact on the quality of learning and teachers' ability to adapt to the different needs of learners at each level of education.

At the primary level, the role of the teacher dominates with 80%, while the learners are only 20%. This shows that teachers play a central role in delivering material to students. At the junior high school level, the proportion of roles changes to 60% for teachers and 40% for learners, indicating an increase in student participation. At the senior high school level, the division of roles is more balanced with 40% for teachers and 60% for learners, indicating that students have a more active role. Finally, at the university student level, the proportion of roles reversed, with 20% for teachers and 80% for learners, reflecting students' independence and activeness in public speaking activities.

Despite the difference in the percentage of roles between teachers and learners, this study highlights a significant gap in the development of public speaking skills for educators, which is crucial to support effective communication in education. Public speaking for educators is not just about how to speak in front of the class, but rather how they can deliver material clearly, motivate learners, and create effective interactions (Simbolon, 2024). Unfortunately, many public speaking trainings conducted for educators tend to be temporary and unsustainable. These trainings often focus only on developing basic public speaking skills, with no follow-up or follow-up programs to ensure that teachers actually master and develop these abilities over time. Continuous development in public speaking skills is essential because the world of education is constantly changing and requires teachers who can adapt to a variety of different communication situations, whether with students, parents or colleagues (Zafirah, et al. 2024).

It should also be noted that each level of education has different needs and challenges regarding the public speaking role of an educator (Bazarbayevna, 2024). In

primary education, for example, a teacher may speak more often in front of students as they play a central role in delivering materials and managing the class. Meanwhile, in secondary or higher education, teachers may play more of a facilitator role where learners participate more actively in discussions or presentations (Kusuma et al., 2024). Therefore, it is important to understand that a teacher's public speaking needs may vary by education level, but effective communication skills remain a key element required at all levels.

However, professional mastery of public speaking can have a significant impact on the quality of learning (Wiratama, 2021). With good public speaking, an educator can provide more effective feedback to learners, help them understand the material better, and encourage active participation in the learning process. A teacher's ability to speak clearly, confidently, and attract students' attention can create a more interactive and dynamic learning atmosphere. Learners who are actively involved in listening and participating in class tend to have higher learning motivation and achieve better academic results (Karina, et al, 2024).

In addition, strong public speaking skills can also improve a teacher's overall performance. Teachers who are able to speak professionally in public not only have the ability to manage the classroom better, but can also model good communication for students (Wulandari & Nurhaliza, 2023). They are able to deliver instructions more clearly, respond to questions more appropriately, and facilitate meaningful discussions. This all contributes to better achievement of educational goals, where students not only understand the material but are also inspired to learn more. Therefore, investment in the ongoing development of public speaking for educators is necessary to ensure that they can meet the demands of an increasingly complex educational world.

Therefore, from the data shown in the diagram above, we can draw a new finding that although the proportion of educators in public speaking activities is decreasing at higher levels, this indicates a need to:

- 1) Give greater attention to public speaking training for educators at all levels of education.
- 2) Establish a continuous development program that not only provides basic training, but also adapts training to the challenges and changes faced by educators.

- 3) Integrate public speaking as an integral part of professional development for educators, so that they can become more effective role models and facilitators in helping students develop their communication skills.

D. CONCLUSION

The reviewed research shows that public speaking skills are essential in 21st century education, both for educators and learners. They support better interaction, increase learning motivation and foster critical thinking skills. In addition, public speaking training has been shown to improve speaking skills in both educators and learners. Students who participated in the training showed increased confidence and communication skills, while educators became more effective in delivering materials and interacting with students. However, there are gaps in the research related to developing public speaking skills in educators, especially in terms of unsu stainable training. To address this, it is recommended that training programs be more integrated and sustainable, with adjustments to the challenges faced by educators at various levels of education.

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